

PREDICTION OF FATIGUE LIFE FOR MATRIX DOMINATE COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

Fatigue life for matrix dominate composite laminates under constant amplitude tensile fatigue loading can be predicted theoretically based on a modified stiffness degradation model along with an appropriate failure criterion. The modified stiffness degradation used in this study take account of the effect of nonlinear stress-strain relation and plastic deformation which are significant for matrix dominate composites under fatigue cycling. The failure criterion used herein states that a laminates fails when its fatigue stiffness reduces a certain amount. Using the modified stiffness degradation model and the failure criterion, analytical model for the distribution of fatigue life for matrix dominate composites is derived. Experiments were also conducted on $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ graphite/epoxy laminate to verify the theoretical model. Correlations between the analytical predictions and experimental results are shown to be quite reasonable.

KEYWORDS: Fatigue; Stiffness Degradation; Failure Criterion; Life Prediction;
Matrix Dominate Composites.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unlike metals exhibit one failure mode, a major crack initiates and propagates until failure occurs, under fatigue loading, the fatigue failure mode of composites consists of many cracks including fiber breakage, matrix cracking, fiber-matrix debonding, void growth and delamination. Any one or combination of these various mechanism may lead to the reduction of overall stiffness and strength or other degradations. Thus, fatigue failure is a progressive process. During this process, the overall stiffness and strength reduce progressively until its values can no longer resist the applied loading and total failure occurs. Unless the relationship between various damage mechanism is

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clearly understood and the degradation of material characteristic quantities as well as the fatigue life are predictable, composites can not be used with confidence.

Many research efforts have been performed to quantify fatigue damage in global sense through the measure of residual strength [1-10] or stiffness [11-24]. Using either residual strength or stiffness degradation characteristics, together with a appropriate failure criterion, the fatigue life of composite laminates can be predicted. The latter quantity is used in the present study to predict the fatigue life, since it can be measured nondestructively in service, while the measurement of the residual strength is destructive.

Recently, Yang et al. [22] developed a stiffness degradation model which has been used successfully to predict the residual stiffness for fiber dominate composites. Their model was also verified by experiments. They also proposed a failure stiffness criterion to predict the fatigue life based on this stiffness degradation model [23]. Later, the authors [24] modified this model to account for the nonlinear stress-strain relation and plastic deformation for matrix dominate composites. Due to viscoelastic properties and nonlinear stress-strain relation for matrix dominate composites, the criterion at fatigue failure is not same as that for fiber laminate composites. A new empirical failure criterion is proposed in this paper. Then, based on the new failure criterion and modified stiffness degradation model in Ref. 24, a statistical model for predicting of the distribution of fatigue life is derived. Experiments were also performed on $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ graphite/epoxy laminates to verify the fatigue life predictions from the theoretical model. It is shown that comparisons between theoretical predictions and experimental results are reasonable.

2. MODIFIED STIFFNESS DEGRADATION MODEL

A residual stiffness degradation model was proposed by Yang et al. [22] for fiber dominate composite laminates. The authors have been extended the stiffness degradation model by using fatigue stiffness [19,21] to account for the matrix dominate composites,

$$F(n) = F_{0,S}(1 - Qn^v) \quad (1)$$

where $F(n)$ is the residual fatigue stiffness at load cycle n , $F_{0,S}$ is the initial fatigue stiffness and Q and v are two random variables. Based on this modified stiffness degradation model, the fatigue modulus $F(n)$ (defined as the applied stress level S divided by the corresponding strain at the n -th loading cycle) at any arbitrary fatigue cycle n can be expressed in terms of the initial fatigue stiffness $F_{0,S}$ and two random variables Q and v which depend on the applied stress level, loading frequency, stress ratio and environment, etc. The subscript S in $F_{0,S}$ denotes that the initial fatigue stiffness depends on the applied stress level S . Experimental results have shown that Q and v are highly linearly correlated, their relation can be expressed as

$$Q = a_1 + a_2 v, \quad (2)$$

where a_1 and a_2 are parameters independent of the applied stress level. Experimental data further indicate that v is a linear function of applied stress level S and can be expressed as

$$v = a_3 + BS \quad (3)$$

where a_3 is a parameter and B is a random variable. Substitution of Eqs. (2) and (3) into (1) yields

$$F(n) = F_{0,S} [1 - (d + a_2 BS)n^{a_3 + BS}] \quad (5)$$

where $d = a_1 + a_2 a_3$.

It is more desirable to express the initial fatigue stiffness $F_{0,S}$ with the initial tangent stiffness $E(0)$ at 0-th cycle, since $E(0)$ is independent of applied stress level S . This can be done by relating the tangent stiffness and fatigue stiffness at 0-th cycle through the nonlinear stress-strain relation [25].

$$\sigma = \beta(1 - e^{-r\epsilon}), \quad (6)$$

where β and r are parameters. Thus,

$$F_{0,S} = g(S)E(0) \quad (7)$$

where $g(S)$ is function of applied stress level S ,

$$g(S) = \frac{S}{\beta \ln\left(\frac{\beta}{\beta - S}\right)}. \quad (8)$$

The detailed derivation of $g(S)$ can be found in Ref. 24.

Thus, Eq.(5) can be written in the following form

$$F(n) = g(S)E(0)[1 - (d + a_2 BS)n^{a_3 + BS}]. \quad (9)$$

Equation (9) is the modified stiffness degradation model for matrix dominate composite laminates. In Eq. (9), $E(0)$ and B are random variables with lognormal distributions

$$F_{E(0)}(z) = P[E(0) \leq z] = \Phi\left[\frac{\ln z - \mu_0}{\sigma_0}\right]; z \geq 0 \quad (10)$$

$$F_B(b) = P[B \leq b] = \Phi\left[\frac{\ln b - \mu_B}{\sigma_B}\right]; b \geq 0 \quad (11)$$

where $\Phi [\]$ is the standardized normal distribution and μ_0, σ_0 and μ_B, σ_B are mean and standard deviation of $E(0)$ and B , respectively. The parameters d, a_2, a_3 along with $g(S), \mu_0, \sigma_0, \mu_B$ and σ_B are determined from base-line data.

3. PREDICTION OF FATIGUE LIFE

In order to predict the fatigue life for composites based on the modified stiffness degradation model, Eq.(9), a failure criterion should be imposed first. For fiber dominate composites, fatigue failure occurs as the fatigue failure strain reaches the ultimate strain at static test [23]. This criterion is not valid for matrix dominate composites, since its stress-strain relation is highly nonlinear and involves significant plastic deformation during fatigue cycling. Consequently, the fatigue failure strain depends on the applied stress level. Furthermore, the loading rate also affects static failure strain. Hwang and Han [19, 21] proposed another failure criterion. They assumed that failure occurs when the

fatigue stiffness reduced to the secant modulus of static test at failure. Since the static failure strain depends on loading rate, the secant modulus of static test also depends on loading rate. Thus, this criterion is also inadequate for life prediction in the present case.

Under fatigue cycling, the fatigue stiffness $F(n)$ reduces as the number of load cycles n increases. It assumes that a specimen fails when its fatigue stiffness reduces by a certain amount C . This reduced amount of fatigue stiffness C which is independent of the stress level will be determined from experiments. From this assumption, it follows that the fatigue stiffness at failure, $F(N)$, is defined as

$$F(N) = F_{0,S} - C, \quad (12)$$

where N is the fatigue life denoting the number of load cycles to fatigue failure.

Imposing the boundary condition at failure to Eq. (9), i.e., $n = N$ and $F(n) = F(N)$ yields the fatigue life N as follows

$$N = \left[\frac{1 - \frac{F(N)}{g(S)E(0)}}{d + a_2 BS} \right]^{\frac{1}{a_3 + BS}} \quad (13)$$

Equation (12) can be rewritten as

$$1 - \frac{F(N)}{F_{0,S}} = \frac{C}{F_{0,S}} \quad (14)$$

Substituting of Eqs.(7) and (12) into (14), the fatigue life N becomes

$$N = \left[\frac{\frac{C}{g(S)E(0)}}{d + a_2 BS} \right]^{\frac{1}{a_3 + BS}} \quad (15)$$

For a given specimen, the initial tangent stiffness $E(0)$ and the reduced amount of the fatigue modulus C can be measured. The $C/E(0)$ in the above equation can be denoted by another variable W , and Eq.(15) becomes

$$N = \left[\frac{\frac{W}{g(S)}}{d + a_2 BS} \right]^{\frac{1}{a_3 + BS}} \quad (16)$$

W is a random variable (since C and $E(0)$ both are random variables). It has been noted that C and $E(0)$ are independent of stress level, it is inferred that W is also independent of stress level. This inference will be verified by experimental results. In addition, W is assumed to be lognormally distributed. As a result, the fatigue life N is a function of two random variables W and B . Hence, the distribution of N is obtained, from the theorem of total probability,

$$F_N(n) = P[N \leq n] = \int_0^\infty F_W[\Omega(n, b)] f_B(b) db \quad (17)$$

where

$$F_W[\Omega(n, b)] = P[W \leq \Omega(n, b)] = \Phi\left[\frac{\ln[\Omega(n, b)] - \mu_W}{\sigma_W}\right]$$

and

$$\Omega(n, b) = g(S)(d + a_2 b S)n^{a_3 + b S}$$

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

A test program using coupon specimens of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ T300/5208 graphite/epoxy composite laminates was performed for the purpose of determining the model parameters and verifying the theoretical model for predicting fatigue life proposed previously. The nominal dimensions of the specimens were 229 mm (9 in) long, 38 mm (1.5 in) wide and 1.0 mm (0.04 in) thick. All tests were performed on the MTS 880 material testing system with hydraulic grips and a load capacity of 10 metric tons. The applied load and axial strain was monitored by the force and stroke transducer (LVDT) of the test system. Data were recorded using a sixteen-bit PC and specially developed software to measure stress-strain data at predetermined fatigue cycles.

Twenty coupon specimens were tested statically to determine the ultimate tensile strength at a cross head speed of 2.5 cm/sec which would be close to the actual loading rate in the fatigue test. The average ultimate strength of the twenty specimens is 191 MPa with a standard deviation of 8.36 MPa.

Fatigue tests were performed at a loading frequency of 10 Hz, a stress ratio of 0.1, and at five different stress levels. The stress levels selected were 75, 70, 65, 60 and 55% of the static ultimate strength, corresponding to maximum applied stresses, S , of 143.25, 133.70, 124.15, 114.6 and 105.05 MPa. Total number of 58 specimens were tested. Twelve specimens were tested at each applied stress levels 143.25, 133.70 and 105.05 MPa, whereas eleven specimens were tested at maximum applied stresses 124.15 and 114.6 MPa, respectively. During fatigue test, forces and displacements were monitored and measured at preassigned load cycles. Fatigue test for each specimen was performed continuously until the specimen failed. The fatigue life cycle N was recorded and the failure fatigue stiffness $F(N)$ was measured. After failure, each specimen was scrutinized carefully for the failure surface. It was shown that the failure mode of $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ laminates was dominated by delamination and matrix failure. No obvious differences in the failure mode for different applied stress levels.

5. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The methodologies and predictive capabilities described in previous sections are verified by experimental data. The reduction amount C of fatigue stiffness was measured and fatigue life N was recorded for each specimen under fatigue test. Then, the nondimensionalized quantity W were calculated. The W is assumed to be lognormally distributed with mean $\mu_W = -1.2043$ and standard deviation $\sigma_W = 0.08463$. Figure 1 shows the relation of W versus stress level S . It can be seen that W is independent of stress level.

Five data sets obtained in fatigue test are used to verify the theoretical prediction of the fatigue life distribution. Data sets associated with the maximum stress levels 105.05,

124.15, 114.60, 133.70 and 143.25 MPa are designated as data sets No. 1, No. 2, No. 3, No. 4 and No. 5, respectively. Any four of the five data sets will be considered as base-line data from which $\sigma_0, \mu_0, \sigma_B, \mu_B$ and $g(S)$ and model parameters are estimated. Then the derived statistical distribution of the fatigue life, Eq. (15), will be employed to predict the distribution of the fatigue life for the remained data set. Procedures to determine $\sigma_0, \mu_0, \sigma_B, \mu_B$ and $g(S)$ as well as model parameters a_1, a_2 , and a_3 have been given in Ref. 24. The results for different base-line data sets are listed in Table 1. In addition, the mean and standard deviation of $\ln W$, i.e., μ_W and σ_W , respectively, are also shown in Table 2 for different base-line data sets.

The predicted distribution of fatigue life for each data set can be made using base-line data given in Tables 1 and 2. For example, if the fatigue life distribution of the specimen under stress level $S = 105.05$ Mpa is to be predicted, the parameters of base-line data sets No. 2,3,4 and 5 that listed in the first row of Tables 1 and 2 are substituted into Eq. (15) to integrate for the results. The predicted fatigue life distributions are shown in Fig. 2 as solid line and the experimental data are also shown as solid circles for comparison. The same procedures can be applied to other stress levels to predict the fatigue life distributions. Figures 3-6 presents the theoretical predictions together with the experimental results. It should be pointed out that there was one specimen at $S = 105.05$ MPa which did not fail at 10^6 cycles, and the test was terminated deliberately. Hence this data should be located on the right hand side of its current position, as indicated by an arrow.

It is observed from Figs. 2-6 that the correlations between the theoretically predicted fatigue life distributions and the experimental test results are quite reasonable. The theoretical predictions for the fatigue life seem to involve larger statistical variability than the experimental data for lower stress levels.

6. CONCLUSIONS

An empirical failure criterion has been postulated for the matrix dominate composite laminates. This criterion states that a specimen under fatigue cycling will fail after its fatigue stiffness reduces a certain amount which is independent of the stress level. Theoretical prediction of the distribution of fatigue life can be made based on this failure criterion and a modified stiffness degradation model for matrix dominate composites under constant amplitude tension-tension fatigue loading. An experimental program has been performed using $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ graphite/epoxy laminates to generate statistically meaningful data for the verification of the theoretical prediction. It is shown that the correlations between the theoretically predicted fatigue life distributions and the experimental results are very reasonable.

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Table 1 Summary of parameters for different base-line data sets

base-line data set	$g(S)$	a_1	a_2	a_3	μ_0	σ_0	μ_B	σ_B
No.2, 3, 4, 5	0.7792	0.1579	-0.3054	-0.5707	3.0838	0.03166	1.7487	0.04351
No.1, 3, 4, 5	0.7600	0.1466	-0.2535	-0.3557	3.0758	0.03663	1.4120	0.04648
No.1, 2, 4, 5	0.7377	0.1437	-0.2446	-0.3677	3.0727	0.03374	1.4424	0.04405
No.1, 2, 3, 5	0.7147	0.1459	-0.2479	-0.3690	3.0722	0.03683	1.4378	0.03746
No.1, 2, 3, 4	0.6841	0.1479	-0.2651	-0.3033	3.0748	0.03219	1.2895	0.03663

Table 2 Mean and standard deviation of $\ln W$ for different base-line data sets

base-line data set	mean	standard deviation
No.2, 3, 4, 5	-1.1972	0.08874
No.1, 3, 4, 5	-1.1963	0.09092
No.1, 2, 4, 5	-1.2025	0.09178
No.1, 2, 3, 5	-1.2179	0.07936
No.1, 2, 3, 4	-1.2078	0.06675
No.1, 2, 3, 4, 5	-1.2043	0.08463

Fig. 1 Nondimensionalized W at different stress levels

Fig. 2 Correlation between predicted fatigue life distribution and experimental results; $S = 105.05 MPa$

Fig. 3 Correlation between predicted fatigue life distribution and experimental results; $S = 114.60MPa$

Fig. 4 Correlation between predicted fatigue life distribution and experimental results; $S = 124.15MPa$

Fig. 6 Correlation between predicted fatigue life distribution and experimental results; $S = 143.25MPa$

Fig. 5 Correlation between predicted fatigue life distribution and experimental results; $S = 133.70MPa$

